

THE METHODS OF TEACHING SPEAKING TO B2 LEVELS

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Abstract: The current paper attempts to examine the various aspects of the discussion and debate methods of teaching at university and its role in enhancing students' linguistic and academic skills. The discussion and debate methods allow establishing a rapport with students, stimulating their critical thinking and articulating ideas clearly, to heighten collaborative learning skills as well as ameliorating their speaking skills to the higher step than they are (from B2 to C1). The findings showed that majority of respondents indicated that a good opportunity to interact is provided during the discussion, debate and that the lecturer is not the sole authority in class. The implications of this research could be reflected on students' learning through their participation in discussion and debate

Key words: Debates, discussion, teaching, critical thinking, collaborative learning, method, speaking skills, B2 levels, strategies, imitation, WebQuest technology.

INTRODUCTION

Speaking is one of the important skills in language learning besides listening, writing and reading. Speaking is activity in giving and asking information as if dialoguing by two or more people.

Based on the result of interview with English teacher of SMA Negeri 1 Lasusua on March 2015, it found kinds of student problem in learning English, especially in speaking. The teacher said that his students cannot express their idea, they were afraid to make mistake and did not have enough vocabulary. He should prepare a good technique in conducting their teaching to motivate the students to speak English.

Based on the explanation above, the researcher is interested in conducting the research entitled "Improving students' speaking skill through debate technique..." [2].

The discussion method could be one of the available teaching methods utilised by university lecturers to promote learning. However, the dynamics of the discussion technique may not be realized by most of these lecturers. Research on the efficiency of group discussion methods has shown that team learning and student-led discussions produce favorable student performance outcomes, and foster greater participation, self-confidence and leadership ability [1].

Debate.

Debate is a teaching strategy to improve verbal communication and critical thinking skills. Debate is presented as a valuable learning activity for teaching critical thinking and improving communication skills. Debating is an effective pedagogical strategy because of the level of responsibility for learning and active involvement required by all student debaters. Debate can motivate students' thinking, moreover if they must defend their stand or opinion which is in contradiction with them. This strategy can involve all students to be active, not only debate performer.

Oros says debates can be integrated into course design and assessment and introduced

to students from the beginning of a module. For these academics, debates can be used to complement other teaching strategies and provide a variety of teaching styles to keep students actively engaged in content.

Most students in Goodwin's research appeared to be happy to participate in debates. Students appear to value the development of skills such as communication and collaborative and critical thinking skills. However, previous research also highlights design concerns that need to be considered such as whether students feel comfortable in defending their position in debates in an argumentative environment; whether students value debates over traditional teaching methods as a teaching strategy; whether all students gain from the debate process and whether the assessment process is effective for the students and the module. Despite critical reflections on the use of debates Kennedy found that around 85% of students would consider participating in future debate opportunities.

Jackson emphasises that lecturers need to seek experiences for students that will increase their critical thinking and problem solving skills, as well as the art of communication in teaching sessions. The use of debates can enhance critical thinking skills such as defining the problem, assessing the credibility of sources, identifying and challenging assumptions, recognising inconsistencies and prioritizing the relevance and salience of various points with the overall argument and enables students to develop their knowledge of social issues, consider multiple viewpoints and accept that, as individuals, there will be differing perspectives on any topic area. Importantly, students need to engage in research to develop their understanding of evidence that aligns with either the for or the against perspective in the debates [2].

Debate was proven one of the best method from my experience. While the time I studied college, I turned to the habit going to the National libraray called Alisher Navai for participating debate in speking club. In that time I completed all grammer rules in English, but I couldn't use them, even I couldn't speak well. When I started to speak, I always thought about grammer, organizing the sentences as well as I was a kind of person who was shy to communicate in English. Because I had a concept "When I do mistake while my speech, other participants laugh on me and I feel myself in discomfort zone". However when I started taking part in debate, everything changed in a good way. I gave so many questions to myself like "Look, they are speaking as much as they can", "You are person like them", "They are doing, so you can do", "Don't shy, shying is your enemy", "If you don't do it right now, you have no chance again to do it anymore" after observing speking club members. To be honest their determination motivated me a lot. First time I wrote my ideas on a paper and read it. Next time I read pretty and I spoke without looking at my written version. Then I commenced to express my opinions without thinking grammer. Debating method not only helped me improving speaking skills but also it caused extending my horizons. That is why I find debate is the one of the best way to ameliorate speking skills whose level is B2 as well as critical thinking and general English.

Imitation.

Imitating is one of the great way amilioriating speaking abilities as native speakers. You feel that you have a growth in your speaking when you turned imitation to your everyday exercises as well as you start to speak automatically. Imitation (material is not changed or changed pretty) and showing attitude using information resources (pictures, cinema and

diafilms...) as well as based on learnt topic [3].

WebQuest technology.

WebQuest technology is one of the sample for improving communication skills. Living modern world, this method is more appropriate because of a lot of things is by internet". At the initial stage of experimental work, various resources for the development of speaking skills in the upper grades were also studied and topics for practice were analyzed as well as was selected. In addition, since WebQuest technology is closely related to the Internet, Internet sources were also studied. So, at this stage, 2 WebQuest tasks were prepared based on the students' interests and were divided into 2 topics. Then, within the selected WebQuest topics, various Internet sources were searched and studied, tasks were prepared in Word program in advance. The main purpose of these tasks was to develop speaking skills in students and be able to express their thoughts freely, and the tasks were adapted to their interests" [4].

Discussion.

Generally speaking, 'discussion' could be considered an activity which involves written or oral expression of different points of view in a given situation. Also, Brookfield and Preskill define it as an alternately serious and playful effort by a group of two or more to share views and engage in mutual and reciprocal critique. Proper discussion would assist learner participants to reach a critically informed understanding of the topic, self-awareness and capacity for self-critique, appreciation of diversity, and informed action.

The discussion process is not merely controlled by one individual presentation as the case in the lecture. The lecturer as the discussion leader may try to strike a balance between controlling the group and letting students air their views with no restrictions. Participation in a class discussion can be voluntary to avoid embarrassment of shy or introvert participants and would be achieved by creating a supportive climate.

In a university class, discussion could be among the common strategies which would be used by lecturers to stimulate active learning. It can offer the lecturer an opportunity to check students' understandings of the material and comprehending ideas thoroughly through expressing their own viewpoints and questions. Sybing reports that discussions provide students with a platform to participate in their learning process. When students are actively involved in using the relevant material, learning would be more interesting for them and students would be more motivated.

Han emphasizes that a sufficient knowledge base established prior to discussion tasks is essential to learner participation. When students gain confidence in their knowledge, then they are more motivated to participate freely in the oral discussion.

Discussion approaches are appropriate to a number of objectives which include providing the lecturer feedback about students' learning; meeting higher-order cognitive objectives, such as application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. These approaches also help students develop their interests and values and change attitudes as well as allowing students to become more active contributors to their own learning.

Lecturers' performance also declines over an hour. Lecturing may be less effective than discussion or individual work in class as there is a lack of concentration on the part of students.

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may not be realized by most of these lecturers. Research on the efficiency of group discussion methods has shown that team learning and student-led discussions produce favorable student performance outcomes, and foster greater participation, self-confidence and leadership ability [1].

Conclusion

The study indicated that the discussion and debate methods improve students' ability to think and could be more tempting to learning than mere listening to a lecture. It may also assist in fostering intellectual growth, individual expression and character development. It offers students opportunities to exchange thoughts and views with each other and heightens language proficiency through constant reinforcement and use.

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